

Introduction

The quality of social cohesion largely depends on interactions, networks, and integration processes among different social groups. Socio-cultural participation is a prerequisite for the formation of these social relations (Schiefer and Noll, 2016). However, political, media, and social debates regarding recent societal developments indicate that social cohesion is becoming increasingly fragile in Western societies, resulting in tendencies of eroding social ties and growing polarization. Against this backdrop and in times of increasing migration (McAuliffe and Triandafyllidou, 2022), the topic of ethnic diversity is becoming central. According to theories on social capital (Putnam, 2000, 2007) and to empirical work (Savelkoul et al., 2011), the key question is whether societies with high immigration rather face conflicts or bonding experiences between ethnic minority and majority groups. The former can arise due to competing values, goals, and actions (conflict theory), the latter due to increased contact between different ethnic groups fostering social cohesion (contact theory).

Cross-ethnic friendships in particular, as strong ties of social capital (Lorenz et al., 2021), have been connected to a variety of outcomes. Generally, cross-group contact is associated with positive beliefs about the other group (Forbes et al., 2024). This holds true especially for non-immigrants: The more immigrant friends they have, the more positive their perception of immigrants (Kende et al., 2024). Also, they have more positive attitudes towards those immigrants who have non-immigrant friends (Bergamaschi and Santagati, 2019; Igarashi and Creighton, 2024). In turn, anti-immigrant attitudes can negatively affect social cohesion (Dirksmeier, 2024). Overall, intergroup contact can foster mutual understanding and trust, making cross-ethnic friendships crucial for the integration of immigrant students into the education system and society.

Participation in cultural activities is not only a central objective of education systems (Werfhorst, 2014) but also key to social cohesion in democratic societies (Putnam, 2000). Culture has been identified as one relevant field to foster social cohesion (Jeannotte, 2003; Jenson, 2002). Cultural tastes (Nagel et al., 2011) as well as joint cultural activities (Hajisoteriou and Angelides, 2016) have been shown to impact adolescents' friendships. Thus, the question arises as to what extent they can contribute to cross-ethnic friendships and, consequently, social cohesion.

Taking this as a starting point, we aim to study three main aspects: [1] During adolescence, important friendships are formed that might affect future directions of social capital at both the individual and societal levels. In a longitudinal design, we analyze the development of cross-ethnic friendships during adolescence. [2] Considering that schooling plays a

significant role in these socialization processes by bringing together youth from diverse backgrounds, we study a secondary school population. [3] With regard to changes over time, the effects of cultural participation have received little attention in the literature. In sum, we examine whether participation in cultural activities affects the longitudinal development of cross-ethnic friendships in a secondary school population.

Our analyses are based on data from secondary school students in the German education system, which exemplifies an ethnically diverse context, facing immigration and increasingly heterogeneous learning environments in recent years. Focusing on cultural participation allows us to study the mechanisms of creating social relations and the potential of cultural interventions to promote both bonding and bridging social cohesion.

Cross-Ethnic Friendships in Adolescents

During adolescence, the formation of friendships and the importance of these new reference groups play a central role in the development of individuals' identities. Compared to childhood, friendships become more nuanced and companionate, primarily fostering emotional socialization (Crosnoe, 2000). Youth make friends in their everyday life contexts and social environments, spaces, and social groups, such as neighborhoods and schools. Thus, "friendships are far from random; instead, they are guided by opportunities to meet and by forces that increase attraction" (Crosnoe, 2000: 381). Generally, individuals tend to form friendships with those they perceive as similar (Schachner et al., 2016). Although the processes of national/ethnic identification are complex (Schlette et al., 2024; Schulz and Leszczensky, 2016), this can be expected to also apply to friendships across ethnic groups. Here, the "cultural, social and physical distance perceived by the natives, and the different language and religion of the immigrants constitute the major sources of prejudice and racism" (Prokic, 2020: 2). As demonstrated for various country settings (for the U.S.: Moody, 2001; for four European countries: Smith et al., 2016), homophily effects are strong. Accordingly, youth from the same ethnic minorities tend to build co-ethnic friendship networks.

Empirical research suggests that, besides general social segregation, schools determine the social networks of adolescents (Moody, 2001; Zhao, 2023). In educational contexts, individual characteristics have been attributed to cross-ethnic friendships. Chavez et al. (2021) find that perspective-taking as a socio-emotional skill is associated with an increased probability to form cross-ethnic friendships in Chilean students. In a quantitative study from Austria, Stefanek et al. (2014) show that the country of origin and the overall number of friends predict friendship preferences on the individual level. Also investigating classroom variables, they find that classroom diversity fosters co-ethnic friendship preferences in Austria. Bagci et al. (2014) present contradictory evidence for London,

finding that classroom diversity fosters cross-ethnic friendships. The latter is confirmed for the U.S. context by Chan and Benner (2025), and additionally they find that immigrant students who perceive the interracial climate at a school in a positive way have more diverse friendships. For the tracked school system of Germany, Faas (2008) shows in a qualitative study that academic track schools promote multicultural values more strongly than vocational track schools. In sum, the education system makes substantial contributions to the formation of cross-ethnic friendships.

Besides the formal education system, potential to shape cross-ethnic friendships lies in extracurricular and leisure-time activities. In particular, cultural activities have been identified as one relevant field to foster social cohesion (Jeannotte, 2003; Jenson, 2002). “Students are more likely to choose each other as friends when they have similar tastes in culture” (Nagel et al., 2011: 424). A range of, predominantly qualitative, studies support the claim that cultural activities foster cross-ethnic friendships: For the UK, Ritchie and Gaulter (2018) find that dance activities foster immigrant students’ sense of belonging. Multiple studies confirm this finding for music, dance, and theater classes in Norway (Rinde and Kenny, 2021; Skyllstad, 1996, 2000). For Cyprus, it has been shown that collaborative art-making fosters cross-ethnic friendships (Hajisoteriou and Angelides, 2016). In a study from the Netherlands, Otte (2019) finds that attending art events that challenge societal norms is associated with intergroup contact. Thus, cultural participation and arts education activities can be expected to foster the development of cross-ethnic friendships.

Overall, the literature has identified many predictors of cross-ethnic friendships and reveals research gaps at the same time. Following contact theory (Allport, 1954), co-ethnic friendships and networks are not static but can change longitudinally. Exposure to individuals from other social groups, i.e. interactions (Ghiglinio and Tabasso, 2024), may increase openness and cross-ethnic friendships over time. As research in the Swedish school system shows, the integration of different friendship networks “might reduce levels of homophily in the subsequent evolution of friendships” (Zhao, 2023). The current literature about the role of cultural participation is limited mainly in two regards: First, it remains unclear whether arts activities can change the longitudinal development of cross-ethnic friendships. Second, although mostly qualitative research provides valuable insights about the relationship between arts activities and cross-ethnic friendships, the validity and generalizability should be tested. Taken together, this calls for a longitudinal design using large-scale panel data.

Social Cohesion and Cultural Participation

Social cohesion can be defined on a general level as “the on going process of developing well-being, sense of belonging, and voluntary social participation of the members of

society, while developing communities that tolerate and promote a multiplicity of values and cultures, and granting at the same time equal rights and opportunities in society” (Fonseca et al., 2018: 246). In a more specific definition pointing to different dimensions of social cohesion, Otte (2019) distinguishes between bonding and bridging as well as ideational and relational social cohesion (Figure 1). *Bonding* refers to internal social cohesion, meaning that relationships within a community or social group are strengthened. *Bridging*, on the other hand, can also be described as external social cohesion and refers to relationships between different communities or social groups. Both bonding and bridging can occur on an ideational and a relational level. The *ideational* level of social cohesion refers to abstract macro-level relationships between large groups of people which can, for example, manifest in values and attitudes towards social groups. *Relational* social cohesion refers to specific interactions on a micro-level which can for example manifest in friendships. The combinations of these two dimensions can be visualized on a quadrant diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Quadrant diagram: Bonding and bridging in ideational and relational social cohesion as proposed in Otte, 2019, p. 4

This concept can be applied to students’ friendships. Clearly, the relational dimension is more relevant here than the ideational one, but bonding and bridging can both apply to students’ friendships. On the one hand, non-immigrant students can foster bonding social cohesion by having friendships with other non-immigrant youth, which results in homogeneous relations. Friendships between immigrants and non-immigrants represent heterogeneous relations and may therefore foster bridging social cohesion. For friendships

between immigrant students, the concept is more complex: If individuals have friends from the same immigrant community they belong to, they foster homogeneous relations. If they make friends who belong to a different immigrant community, they foster heterogeneous relations. In assimilation theories (Portes, 1998; Portes and Rumbaut, 2001), it is argued that social ties with majority-group members enhance the structural integration of ethnic minority members. Thus, friendships between immigrants and non-immigrants can not only contribute to the relational but indirectly also to the ideational dimension. In conclusion, both bonding and bridging forms of social cohesion may emerge from friendships between immigrants and non-immigrants.

Many factors contribute to social cohesion, among them culture. According to French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu, there are three relevant forms of capital in social relationships: besides economic capital in terms of monetary goods, social and cultural capital have been made relevant for social relations and social inequalities (Bourdieu, 1986). Social capital is understood as the network one can access for support. Cultural capital refers to one's cultural tastes, cultural possessions and education. While Bourdieu views social capital as an individual property, it can also be understood as a collective trait of large social groups (Coleman, 1988). The latter can result from individual social capital (Rogošić and Baranović, 2016). This highlights the similarities between the concepts of social capital and social cohesion: Both can be applied to micro and macro levels of society and do overlap to a large extent. According to Bourdieu, the three forms of capital can be transformed into one another. For example, cultural objects like musical instruments can be bought with economic capital. Also, cultural capital gives access to certain social groups and thus can be transformed into social capital (see An and Western, 2019 for a study of conversion between social and cultural capital). How cultural capital is related to social cohesion, is reflected in the fact that ideas from Putnam's famous book *Bowling alone* (Putnam, 2000) were applied to the role of culture in *Singing alone* (Jeannotte, 2003).

In sum, we can expect culture to play a crucial role in social cohesion. However, given that cultural tastes and social networks shape each other reciprocally (Lizardo, 2006), we expect differences due to the specific tastes associated with each cultural activity. There is a contradiction between the mere participation and the expected effect of cultural participation on social cohesion. For example, highbrow cultural activities such as going to classical concerts or theaters are known to be socially selective. Thus, one is unlikely to meet underprivileged people there. For people from the community that does frequently attend such events, they can foster *bonding* social cohesion on the one hand. On the other hand, they can also foster *bridging* cohesion. This can be expected for people from outside the typical community of a specific cultural event and, less obviously, also for people from within this community: Highbrow activities are typically understood as an indicator of high cultural capital. Since cultural capital comes with egalitarian attitudes (Vassenden and

Jonvik, 2018), one could also expect people to become more open towards heterogeneous relations and thus foster *bridging* social cohesion. Moreover, in masscultural events, it is expected that people from diverse backgrounds meet. Thus, these events might be especially well-suited for *bridging* social cohesion (Laurence, 2020). These contradictions in potential effects of masscultural and highbrow cultural events remain under-researched.

Research Questions

Applying the aforementioned theoretical arguments to the question of friendships between immigrant and non-immigrant students, we can generally expect cultural activities to be one source for them to emerge. The effects of each cultural activity can differ depending on the individual's immigrant status. Socially selective highbrow activities, which are typically associated with ethnic majority groups, can be expected to foster bridging social cohesion in immigrant students, while for non-immigrants the bonding effects might be stronger. Researching these interactions between immigrant status and the social selectiveness of cultural activities is the main goal of this paper. Our research questions are:

- How do various cultural activities affect friendships between non-immigrant and immigrant students?
- Do these effects differ for students with and without immigrant background?

Data and Methods

Data: NEPS Starting Cohort 3

The German National Educational Panel Study (NEPS, Blossfeld and Roßbach, 2019) starting cohort 3 dataset was used (SC3, dataset version 13.0.0, NEPS Network, 2024). For this cohort, schools were randomly sampled from all school types in all federal states of Germany. At each school, two fifth grade classes were sampled at random. The initial sample consisted of 5,753 students. In most federal states, the transition from primary to secondary school is after grade 4. However, in Berlin and Brandenburg, the transition is after grade 6. To maintain the representativeness of the school types in these two states, a refreshment sample was taken in wave 3. Data collection started in 2010, when students were on average 11 years old. Since then, data have been collected in 13 waves. NEPS offers a wide array of variables from students, parents, school principals as well as teachers.

In our final sample, we included all available cases. Apart from student data, we also utilized administrative sampling information and data from the parent questionnaire. In

total, data from 8,281 students and 5,615 parents were included. The number of available cases varies per variable (see descriptive statistics in Table 1).

Table 1: Summary statistics

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max
Immigrant Friends (W7)	5,015	3.05	1.38	3.00	1	7
Immigrant Friends (W4)	6,433	2.80	1.46	2.00	1	7
Courses	5,480	0.30	0.46	0.00	0	1
Concert	5,566	0.27	0.44	0.00	0	1
Theater	5,576	0.47	0.50	0.00	0	1
Museum	5,573	0.74	0.44	1.00	0	1
Youth Center	5,365	0.06	0.25	0.00	0	1
Immigrant Background	8,085	0.26	0.44	0.00	0	1
Gender Male	8,278	0.52	0.50	1.00	0	1
Parental Education	4,133	4.51	1.99	4.00	0	8
Academic School Type	8,281	0.39	0.49	0.00	0	1
Immigrant Students at School	8,269	0.26	0.21	0.22	0	1

Variables

Dependent Variable

Immigrant Friends. As our dependent variable we used information on the students' share of immigrant friends. The exact question was: "How many people from your circle of friends have a migrant background, i.e. they themselves or at least one parent were born abroad?" Students responded on an ordinal scale from 1 = "none" over 4 = "about half" to 7 = "all". We used information from wave 7 (*t2*) as the dependent variable in all analyses. For our longitudinal analyses, we included the answers to the same question from wave 4 (*t1*).

Predictors

Courses. We included a variable on students' participation in arts education courses during their leisure-time. Students reported in open text fields what kind of courses they

attended. Then, it was coded what educational area these courses belong to (e.g. music, design, technology, for details see Burkhard and Lampel, 2023). From this information we created a binary variable indicating whether the student had attended at least one course in arts education (wave 5).

Concert. As our second predictor we used information on the students' participation in events involving classical music. Students were asked: "In the last 12 months, how often have you done the following things: - visited an opera, a ballet or a classical concert" and responded on a scale from 1 = "never" to 5 = "more than 5 times". We created a binary variable indicating whether the students had reported to have attended such an event at least one time (wave 5, for detailed information on the scale see Goßmann, 2018).

Theater. We further used another item from the same scale on students' visits to theaters. The question was: "In the last 12 months, how often have you done the following things: - visited a theater?" We again created a binary variable indicating whether students reported attending such an event at least once (wave 5).

Museum. Again, from the same scale we used the item on visits to museums and arts exhibitions. Students were asked: "How often have you done the following things in the last 12 months: - visited a museum or an art exhibition?" We again created a binary variable indicating whether the students had reported to have attended such an event at least one time (wave 5).

Youth Center. As our last variable of cultural participation, we utilized information on the students' activities at youth centers. If they had reported to go to youth centers, they were asked: "What kind of activities do they offer [at the youth center] and which of them do you use? - Making music, dancing, acting or other artistic activities". We again created a binary variable indicating whether students reported to engage in arts activities at the youth center or not (wave 6).

Covariates

Immigrant Background. We used information on the student's family background to create a variable on their own immigrant background. We considered an immigrant background to be present if the students themselves or at least one of their parents was born in a country other than Germany.

Gender (male). As an individual control variable, we used information on the students' binary gender (1 = boys, 0 = girls).

Parental Education. As a second individual control variable, we utilized information on the parents' educational attainment. Both parents' highest educational qualification was

available on the CASMIN scale ranging from 1 = “no qualification” to 8 = “university degree”. We created a variable that indicating the highest educational qualification among both parents, following the dominance approach.

Academic School Type. As an institutional control variable, we used information on the school type attended. We again created a binary variable indicating whether the school is an academic track school (*Gymnasium*) or not.

Immigrant Students at School. As our last control variable, we created a variable indicating the share of students with an immigrant background at the school-level. Then, this information was applied to all students attending this school.

Analyses

Before our multivariate analyses, we examined univariate as well as bivariate descriptive statistics. Our variable of interest was the share of immigrant friends among all friends of each student. Since this item has to be interpreted differently for immigrant and non-immigrant students, we created one subsample for each of these groups. Then, we analyzed each subsample with the following steps:

First, we analyzed the effects in the subsample of non-immigrant students. We estimated regression models for each predictor separately and integrated covariates in a step-wise manner. First, we did not use any covariates. Second, we included the individual covariates (Gender, Parental Education). Third, we removed the individual covariates but included the institutional control variables (Academic School Type, Immigrant Students at School). Fourth, we included all covariates as well as all predictors in a full model. Also, we distinguished between cross-sectional and longitudinal effects. For the latter, we included the share of immigrant friends measured in wave 4 (t_1) in addition to the other covariates. After estimating all of these models, we repeated the same for the subsample of immigrant students.

All analyses were carried out in the statistical software R (R Core Team, 2021). In addition, we used further packages. For data wrangling, we used *tidyverse* (Wickham et al., 2019), for our descriptive analyses *psych* (Revelle, 2024) and *corrplot* (Wei and Simko, 2024). Since our data were collected in a nested setting (students within schools), we had to use cluster-robust standard errors. This was achieved by using the *sandwich* (Zeileis et al., 2020) and *lmttest* (Zeileis and Hothorn, 2002) packages. To address missing values in our data, we created 20 imputed datasets using the *mice* (van Buuren and Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011) and *miceadds* (Robitzsch and Grund, 2024) packages. To assess the robustness of our imputations, we re-estimated all models using complete case analysis (see Appendix). Lastly, to increase the reproducibility of our analyses, we used the

groundhog package (Simonsohn and Gruson, 2024) to load all other packages with their versions from 31 January 2025. All R scripts can be downloaded from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19352665>, making our analyses fully reproducible.

Figure 2: Share of students with immigrant background in the whole sample and in cultural activities

Figure 3: Pearson correlations of all variables used

Results

Descriptive Results

Overall, 26% of all students in our sample have an immigrant background. Given that making contact with other (immigrant or non-immigrant) students is only possible when both groups participate in the same activities, we examined participation rates (Figure 2). For their participation rates in cultural activities, we find that it is lower in all cultural activities compared to the whole sample. Of all students who participate in arts education courses outside school, only 18.9% have an immigrant background. The highest participation rate is found for cultural activities at youth centers, where immigrant students make up 22.1% of all students.

We also examined bivariate correlations of all variables used (Figure 3). We find strong associations between the share of immigrant friends at measurement wave 4 and 7. Also, students who themselves have an immigrant background tend to have more immigrant friends. The correlations also point to peer-effects in friendships since the share of immigrant students at the school-level is highly correlated with the individual share of immigrant friends. However, all cultural activities show a slight negative correlation with the share of immigrant friends.

Non-immigrant students

Turning to results from our regression models, we first analyzed the effects in students without immigrant background. None of the cultural activities has a significant effect on friendships with immigrants. When comparing the point estimates of each cultural activity, it is notable that they are highest for cultural activities at youth centers. However, these differences are not statistically significant either. The effects in our longitudinal analyses are generally smaller but show the same tendencies. Overall, we conclude that cultural activities have little impact on immigrant friendships in the subsample of non-immigrant students.

Immigrant Students

In a second step, we analyzed friendships with immigrants in the subsample of students who themselves have an immigration background. Again, we first used no covariates, then individual covariates, institutional covariates, and lastly all covariates. The only significant effect we find is that immigrant students who participate in arts education courses report to have a lower proportion of immigrant friends. This only holds true when there are no covariates. When adding either individual or institutional covariates or making the analysis longitudinal, the effect is no longer significant. Thus, it cannot be considered a robust

result. Comparing the cultural activities to each other, we find the same tendency as in non-immigrant students: the point estimates are lowest for courses outside school and highest for cultural activities at youth centers. However, these differences are not significant again. All in all, we conclude that cultural participation does not have an impact on the friendships with immigrants in the subsample of students who themselves have an immigrant background.

Figure 4: Effects of cultural participation on the students' share of immigrant friends in non-immigrant students

* Note. Individual control variables: gender, parental education; institutional control variables: academic school type, share of students with immigrant background at school.

Figure 5: Effects of cultural participation on the students' share of immigrant friends in immigrant students

* Note. Individual control variables: gender, parental education; institutional control variables: academic school type, share of students with immigrant background at school.

Discussion

Based on the relationship between cultural participation and social cohesion among adolescents, we aimed to investigate the role of cultural activities in fostering friendships between immigrants and non-immigrants. More broadly, we were interested in the importance of arts education for social cohesion, which largely depends on social interactions and on integration processes among different social groups. Is cultural participation a relevant predictor in this regard? The results are important for political interventions, especially in times of increasing immigration and debates about eroding social ties.

Friendships are formed and may change during early adolescence, a developmental stage where juveniles encounter different school and leisure-time contexts and friend groups. We analyzed our two research questions - whether cultural activities affect cross-ethnic friendships and if this differs between ethnic majority and minority students - in a longitudinal design: no indications of such associations were found in the German context. We conclude that cultural participation of adolescents has no effect on the formation of friendships between immigrant and non-immigrant secondary school students, nor on co-

ethnic friendships between those who have an immigrant background. Contrary to findings from previous studies (Hajisoteriou and Angelides, 2016; Otte, 2019; Rinde and Kenny, 2021; Ritchie and Gaulter, 2018; Skyllstad, 1996, 2000), we do not find evidence that cultural participation contributes to bonding or bridging social cohesion in the form of co- and cross-ethnic friendships in adolescents.

What might account for these unexpected findings? First and foremost, our descriptive analyses showed that participation rates of immigrant students were lower across all cultural activities compared to non-immigrant students. Moreover, the school context - in our study, the share of immigrant students at the school - predicted the ethnic composition of friendships to a large extent. In this regard, our results confirm the findings of previous research (Bagci et al., 2014; Chan and Benner, 2025). Accordingly, one explanation might be that the social composition of a school so strongly determines cross-ethnic friendships that the effects of cultural participation are negligibly small. Also, one further explanation could be that we mostly used measurements of highbrow activities, which are rather exclusive. However, even for arts activities at youth centers, which have a socially inclusive character in Germany, no effects on cross-ethnic friendships were found. Overall, the finding of a null effect of cultural participation on networks among different ethnic groups holds true. Currently, cultural participation appears to play only a limited role in fostering friendships between immigrant and non-immigrant students. If various cultural activities were more attractive, accessible, or integrative for immigrant youth, effects on cross-ethnic friendships - and in the long run on social cohesion - could be possible.

In future research, several issues could be addressed. First, in our study, we examined the effects of leisure-time activities. Given the importance of the formal school system for adolescents' friendships (Bagci et al., 2014; Faas, 2008), the question arises how cultural activities during leisure-time and formal instruction at school interact with each other. Second, future research could investigate the relevance of cultural activities for other aspects of social cohesion, such as school climate or school belonging (Chan and Benner, 2025; Heppt et al., 2025). This includes measurements of ideational social cohesion like as social trust. Especially, clarifying the extent to which ideational cohesion leads to relational cohesion and vice versa (see Rivas-Drake et al., 2018), would help understand the mechanisms underlying the relationship between cultural participation and social cohesion. Third, the existing literature focuses on observational data. Experimental designs could help strengthen causal claims and clarify the existing contradictions. While we could not address these perspectives in our study due to data availability limitations, they are crucial for understanding the role of cultural participation for social cohesion in heterogeneous school contexts and societies.

References

- Allport GW (1954) *The Nature of Prejudice*. Reading: Addison-Wesley.
- An W and Western B (2019) Social capital in the creation of cultural capital: Family structure, neighborhood cohesion, and extracurricular participation. *Social Science Research* 81. Elsevier BV: 192–208.
- Bagci SC, Kumashiro M, Smith PK, et al. (2014) Cross-ethnic friendships: Are they really rare? Evidence from secondary schools around London. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations* 41. Elsevier BV: 125–137.
- Bergamaschi A and Santagati M (2019) When friendship is stronger than prejudice. Role of intergroup friendships among adolescents in two distinct socio-cultural contexts of immigration. *International Review of Sociology* 29(1). Informa UK Limited: 36–57.
- Blossfeld H-P and Roßbach H-G (eds) (2019) *Education as a Lifelong Process: The German National Educational Panel Study (NEPS)*. 2nd ed. Wiesbaden: Springer VS.
- Bourdieu P (1986) *Distinction. A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. Harvard University Press.
- Burkhard J and Lampel G (2023) *Report on the coding of verbatim answers about courses outside school from the perspective of arts education. NEPS Technical Report*. Bamberg: Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories, National Educational Panel Study.
- Chan M and Benner AD (2025) Promoting cross-racial and ethnic friendships in schools: Roles of school diversity and interracial climate and intersections with immigrant status. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 54(7). Springer Science: 1718–1731.
- Chavez DJ, Palacios D, Luengo-Kanacri BP, et al. (2021) The role of perspective-taking and low social class prejudice on cross-ethnic friendship formation. *New directions for child and adolescent development*. Epub ahead of print 2021.
- Coleman JS (1988) Social capital in the creation of human capital. *American Journal of Sociology* 94. University of Chicago Press: S95–S120.
- Crosnoe R (2000) Friendships in childhood and adolescence: The life course and new directions. *Social Psychology Quarterly* 63(4). SAGE Publications: 377.
- Dirksmeier P (2024) The eroding power of anti-immigrant attitudes for social cohesion in Singapore: More myth than fact? *GeoJournal* 89(6).
- Faas D (2008) From foreigner pedagogy to intercultural education: An analysis of the German responses to diversity and its impact on schools and students. *European Educational Research Journal* 7(1). SAGE Publications: 108–123.

Fonseca X, Lukosch S and Brazier F (2018) Social cohesion revisited: A new definition and how to characterize it. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research* 32. Informa UK Limited: 231–253.

Forbes MB, Kaufman EM, Rumberger J, et al. (2024) Cross-group contact predicts positive beliefs about girls' and black peers' STEM abilities and occupational prospects. *Social Development* 34(1). Wiley.

Ghiglino C and Tabasso N (2024) Endogenous identity in a social network. *arXiv preprint*. Epub ahead of print 2024.

Goßmann F (2018) *Measuring Cultural Capital in the NEPS (NEPS Survey Paper No. 48)*. Bamberg: LfBi Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories.

Hajisoteriou C and Angelides P (2016) Collaborative art-making for reducing marginalisation and promoting intercultural education and inclusion. *International Journal of Inclusive Education* 21(4). Informa UK Limited: 361–375.

Heppt B, Schwarzenenthal M and Scharf J (2025) Discriminatory climate and school adjustment in ethnically minoritized adolescents and majority adolescents: An investigation of the mediating role of teaching quality. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 54(7). Springer Science: 1732–1755.

Igarashi A and Creighton MJ (2024) Does social embeddedness shape attitudes toward migrants? Evidence from a survey experiment in the United Kingdom. *Social Forces*. Epub ahead of print 2024.

Jeannotte S (2003) Singing alone? The contribution of cultural capital to social cohesion and sustainable communities. *International Journal of Cultural Policy* 9(1). Informa UK Limited: 35–49.

Jenson J (2002) Identifying the links: Social cohesion and culture. *Canadian Journal of Communication* 27: 141–151.

Kende J, Feher L, Tropp LR, et al. (2024) Friendship with immigrants and inclusive policies correspond to more positive perceptions of immigrants: A longitudinal multilevel analysis across North America and Europe. *European Journal of Social Psychology*. Wiley. DOI: 10.1002/ejsp.3135.

Laurence J (2020) Cohesion through participation? Youth engagement, interethnic attitudes, and pathways of positive and negative intergroup contact among adolescents: A quasi-experimental field study. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 46(13). Informa UK Limited: 2700–2722.

Lizardo O (2006) How cultural tastes shape personal networks. *American Sociological Review* 71(5). SAGE Publications: 778–807.

Lorenz G, Salikutluk Z, Boda Z, et al. (2021) The link between social and structural integration: Co- and interethnic friendship selection and social influence within adolescent social networks. *Sociological Science* 8. Society for Sociological Science: 371–396.

McAuliffe M and Triandafyllidou A (eds) (2022) *World Migration Report 2022*. Geneva: International Organization for Migration (IOM).

Moody J (2001) Race, school integration, and friendship segregation in America. *American Journal of Sociology* 107(3). University of Chicago Press: 679–716.

Nagel I, Ganzeboom H and Kalmijn M (2011) Bourdieu in the network : The influence of high and popular culture on network formation in secondary school. *Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie* 51: 424–446.

NEPS Network (2024) National educational panel study, scientific use file of starting cohort grade 5 [data set]. Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories (LifBi).

Otte H (2019) Bonding or bridging? On art participation and social cohesion in a rural region of the Netherlands. *Poetics* 76. Elsevier BV: 101355.

Portes A (1998) Social capital: Its origins and applications in modern sociology. *Annual Review of Sociology* 24(1). Annual Reviews: 1–24.

Portes A and Rumbaut RG (2001) *Legacies. The Story of the Immigrant Second Generation*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Prokic M (2020) Immigrants and native families in schools: Reconciling trust and diversity. *GRITIM-UPF Working Paper Series* (45).

Putnam RD (2000) *Bowling Alone: The Collapse and Revival of American Community*. New York: Simon Schuster.

Putnam RD (2007) E pluribus unum: Diversity and community in the twenty-first century. The 2006 Johan Skytte prize lecture. *Scandinavian Political Studies* 30(2).

R Core Team (2021) *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Available at: <https://www.R-project.org/>.

Revelle W (2024) *Psych: Procedures for Psychological, Psychometric, and Personality Research*. Evanston, Illinois: Northwestern University. Available at: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=psych>.

Rinde FB and Kenny A (2021) Music in the school life of newly arrived migrant children: Potential paths to participation and belonging. *Music Education Research* 23(5). Informa UK Limited: 622–633.

Ritchie A and Gaulter A (2018) Dancing towards belonging: The use of a dance intervention to influence migrant pupils' sense of belonging in school. *International Journal of Inclusive Education* 24(4). Informa UK Limited: 366–380.

Rivas-Drake D, Saleem M, Schaefer DR, et al. (2018) Intergroup contact attitudes across peer networks in school: Selection, influence, and implications for cross-group friendships. *Child Development* 90(6). Wiley: 1898–1916.

Robitzsch A and Grund S (2024) *Miceadds: Some Additional Multiple Imputation Functions, Especially for 'Mice'*. Available at: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=miceadds>.

Rogošić S and Baranović B (2016) Social capital and educational achievements: Coleman vs. Bourdieu. *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal* 6(2): 81–100.

Savelkoul M, Gesthuizen M and Scheepers P (2011) Explaining relationships between ethnic diversity and informal social capital across European countries and regions: Tests of constrict, conflict and contact theory. *Social Science Research* 40(4). Elsevier BV: 1091–1107.

Schachner M, Van de Vijver F, Brenick A, et al. (2016) Who is friends with whom? Patterns of inter- and intraethnic friendships of mainstream and immigrant early adolescents in Germany. In: *Unity, diversity and culture*, 2016. International Association for Cross-Cultural Psychology.

Schiefer D and Noll J van der (2016) The essentials of social cohesion: A literature review. *Social Indicators Research* 132(2). Springer Science; Business Media LLC: 579–603.

Schlette A, Stark TH, Smeekes A, et al. (2024) Understanding causes of adolescents' ascriptions of peers' dual ethnic and national belonging. *Journal of Community & Applied Social Psychology*. Epub ahead of print 2024.

Schulz B and Leszczensky L (2016) Native friends and host country identification among adolescent immigrants in Germany: The role of ethnic boundaries. *International Migration Review* 50: 163–196.

Simonsohn U and Gruson H (2024) *Groundhog: Version-Control for CRAN, GitHub, and GitLab Packages*. Available at: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=groundhog>.

Skylstad K (1996) Music in conflict management: Fostering interracial understanding through music. *European Journal of Intercultural Studies* 7(2). Informa UK Limited: 46–56.

Skylstad K (2000) Creating a culture of peace. The performing arts in interethnic negotiations. *Journal of Intercultural Communication* 2(2). International Collaboration for Research; Publications: 1–07.

Smith S, McFarland DA, Van Tubergen F, et al. (2016) Ethnic composition and friendship segregation: Differential effects for adolescent natives and immigrants. *American Journal of Sociology* 121(4). University of Chicago Press: 1223–1272.

Stefanek E, Strohmeier D and Schoot R van de (2014) Individual and class room predictors of same-cultural friendship preferences in multicultural schools. *International Journal of Behavioral Development* 39(3). SAGE Publications: 255–265.

van Buuren S and Groothuis-Oudshoorn K (2011) mice: Multivariate imputation by chained equations in R. *Journal of Statistical Software* 45(3): 1–67.

Vassenden A and Jonvik M (2018) Cultural capital as a hidden asset: Culture, egalitarianism and inter-class social encounters in Stavanger, Norway. *Cultural Sociology* 13(1). SAGE Publications: 37–56.

Wei T and Simko V (2024) *R Package 'Corrplot': Visualization of a Correlation Matrix*. Available at: <https://github.com/taiyun/corrplot>.

Werfhorst HG van de (2014) Changing societies and four tasks of schooling: Challenges for strongly differentiated educational systems. *International Review of Education* 60(1). Springer Science; Business Media LLC: 123–144.

Wickham H, Averick M, Bryan J, et al. (2019) Welcome to the tidyverse. *Journal of Open Source Software* 4(43). The Open Journal: 1686.

Zeileis A and Hothorn T (2002) Diagnostic checking in regression relationships. *R News* 2(3): 7–10.

Zeileis A, Köll S and Graham N (2020) Various versatile variances: An object-oriented implementation of clustered covariances in r. *Journal of Statistical Software* 95(1). Foundation for Open Access Statistic.

Zhao L (2023) Networks in the making: Friendship segregation and ethnic homophily. *Social Science Research* 110: 102813.

Appendix

Results from complete case analysis

Non-immigrant Students

Figure 6: Effects of cultural participation on the students' share of immigrant friends in non-immigrant students (complete case analysis)

* Note. Individual control variables: gender, parental education; institutional control variables: academic school type, share of students with immigrant background at school.

Immigrant Students

Figure 7: Effects of cultural participation on the students' share of immigrant friends in immigrant students (complete case analysis)

* Note. Individual control variables: gender, parental education; institutional control variables: academic school type, share of students with immigrant background at school.